

EVALUATION OF CREATIVITY IN STUDENTS

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Abstract: What is creativity? Can creativity be assessed? If so, how? This article was created as a result of scientific research to find answers to the same and similar questions. The article also comments on approaches to creativity in education.

Key words and phrases: creativity, assessment of creativity, creativity in education, student, creative approach.

INTRODUCTION

When talking about the field of education, if there is a discussion about the existence or development of creativity in its participants, in addition, the topic of creativity assessment, the conversation will inevitably turn into important questions, such as those mentioned above. In these matters, one can see that many people have strong opinions about assessment, particularly standardized assessment. And most of them share the same strong opinion that creativity can or should be measured in this way.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

He was convinced that it is important to set aside some time to clarify the questions asked in the abstract. Rather than simply answering questions with yes or no, making the topic more debated—asking questions that allow for a more nuanced dialogue—can be interesting and useful for both educators and learners in pedagogy and psychology.

was considered. For example: What exactly is meant by assessment? Are

there certain aspects of creativity that are more susceptible to assessment than others? Are there particular approaches to observation, documentation, and measurement that are more or less appropriate for a construct like creativity? Can some assessment approaches help students develop creativity? Why? It's no secret that trends around the world change constantly and very quickly. These trends will not fail to affect education, study, learning, employment and, of course, the life of the whole society. Creativity is a trend that has developed rapidly in the 21st century and is causing many traditions to change. Creativity! Yes, it can be said that it is just a skill. But based on the knowledge based on both theoretical and practical and the results of the research conducted in this regard, below are facts and a wider observation about why creativity is becoming one of the most important factors. First of all, it is necessary to answer what creativity actually is. Creativity - this is a phenomenon that contributes to the creation of something new and useful. In other words, the most necessary tool for creating a new abstract thing (artwork, music, idea or start-up) or physical invention (machine, device or robot) is creativity.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Now, when it comes to creativity assessment, why is it so difficult to deal with the idea of "Creativity Assessment"? Why is the combination of these words marked as a surprising contradiction for many? One reason for the difficulty in integrating assessment and creativity in practice can be argued to be that the mental models of creativity and assessment are incompatible.

EVALUATION OF CREATIVITY

In order to record the result of the creativity assessment, the questionnaire "Creativity assessment" was conducted with the selected respondents. According to the results of the ex-post questionnaire, 13% of the respondents had a low level

of creativity. That is, it can be observed that they have a low level of creativity, independence, non-standard attitude, originality, and flexibility. 50% of the respondents showed a medium level and 37% showed a high level. It can be seen that the students with average level of creativity, non-standard attitude to the problem, creative attitude, creative non-standard approach skills are at an average level, and they are relatively active and meaningful participation in the pedagogical process. It should be noted that the respondents who showed a high level of activity, initiative, organization, original thinking, communication, flexibility of their thoughts.

DISCUSSION

For certain issues, such as creativity and assessment, students' cultural models influence how they integrate reason and practice. The methods and questionnaires used in the study to achieve higher scores also explore students' cultural models, reason and practice. was to form a unity. Assessment of the level of creativity of students studying in higher education institutions and the student team is also reflected in the proper organization of organized lessons.

CONCLUSION

As a result of monitoring the activities of students studying in higher education institutions and the teachers who teach them, interviews conducted with them, questionnaires conducted, students' creative approach, ability to express creative attitude, creative ability skills, research skills and became the basis for the development of certain stage technology of their development.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. Cramond, B. & Wang, L. (2012). The audacity of creativity assessment. In S. Hunsaker (ed.), Identification of students for gifted and talented education services: Theory and practice, pp. 337–361. Mansfield, CT: Creative Learning Press.
2. Dewey, J. (1938/2008). The Later Works of John Dewey, Vol. 4, 1925–

1953: 1929: The Quest for Certainty (Collected Works of John Dewey).
Carbondale, IL: Southern Illinois University Press.

3. Guilford, J. P. (1950). Creativity. *American Psychologist*, 5, pp. 444–454.

4. Wason, P. (1983). Realism and rationality in the selection task. In J. St. B. Evans (Ed.), *Thinking and reasoning: Psychological approaches* (pp. 44–75). London: Routledge & Kegan Paul.

Zimmerman, C. (2000). The development of scientific reasoning skills. *Developmental Review*, 20, 99–149

5. Абдуллаева, Н. Ж., & Комилова, Ф. М. (2020). Значимость формирования организаторских качеств у будущих учителей в развитии современной педагогики. *Наука и образование сегодня*, (6-1 (53)), 42-43.

6. Abdullayeva, N. J. (2020). EXPERIENCE AND THEORETICAL BASES OF INTERNAL CONTROL SERVICE ACTIVITIES IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR. *Экономика и социум*, (5-1 (72)), 13-15.

7. Abdullayeva, N. J. (2020). ISSUES OF REFORMING ACCOUNTING AND REPORTING IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR. *Мировая наука*, (4 (37)), 6-9.